

According to Harned and Owen ("Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", p. 485, Reinhold Pub. 2nd edition) pK_w at 30° is 13.833. Therefore pK_a at $30^\circ = 7.675$ and $K_a = 2.113 \times 10^{-8}$. This compares closely with the value 2.202×10^{-8} for the dissociation constant derived from conductometric determination of the hydrolysis of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, reported previously (*loc. cit.*).

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Received September 24, 1956.

REDUCTION OF DICHROMATE BY FERROCYANIDE

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Much interesting information is available regarding the oxidising properties of $K_2Cr_2O_7$. Its reduction by iodide ions was studied potentiometrically in detail by Gyani and Prasad (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 561; 1955, 32, 313). The reduction of the dichromate ion by the ferrocyanide ion was first studied potentiometrically by Someya (*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1926, 159, 158), who found that the redox reaction

could be followed potentiometrically at 40° - 65° in 5 to 10 c.c. HCl per 60 c.c. of the total volume.

Someya's work refers to strictly specified conditions. The present work was taken up to carry out a fuller investigation of this reaction in different concentrations of two different acids at ordinary temperatures. The use of potassium ferrocyanide for standardisation of potassium permanganate solution is well known. It is of interest to know whether the ferrocyanide itself could be standardised with a readily available substance like $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

A. R. grade $K_2Cr_2O_7$ was taken and prepared for use as usual. Finely powdered crystals of A. R. $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$ were dried to a constant weight over a saturated solution of NaBr (Vogel, "Quantitative Analysis", London, 1951, p. 271). Titrations were carried out in a three-necked Woulff's bottle in which 100 c.c. of 0.005 M solutions of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ in different concentrations of sulphuric acid (12N, 8N, 6N, 4N, 2N, N, N/2, N/4, and N/10) and HCl (2N, N, N/2, and N/4) were taken. The titrations were carried out in the usual manner, using a bright platinum foil electrode at $28^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ for H_2SO_4 mixtures and at $34^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ for HCl mixtures.

The inflexions are quite steep in each case. When sulphuric acid concentrations lie between 6N and 1N or when HCl concentrations lie between N/2 and N/4, the inflexions correspond to 6 moles $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ per mole dichromate and the following mechanism is indicated:

Steady potentials are obtained in 15 to 20 minutes of each addition of the titrant and this period is somewhat longer when the acid concentrations are lower. It appears therefore

that Someya's work cannot only be extended to acids other than HCl but excellent agreement with theoretical requirements may also be obtained at ordinary temperatures under a wide range of acid concentrations.

When sulphuric acid concentration is greater than 6*N* or the HCl concentration is greater than normal, about half a mole less ferrocyanide is required. On the other hand, when sulphuric acid concentration is less than normal, a slight excess over 6 moles ferrocyanide is required. The inflexions are somewhat less steep at lower acid concentrations.

The colour changes of the reaction mixture are very interesting. The initial orange-yellow of the dichromate gradually darkens into a rich golden yellow with a greenish tinge as the ferrocyanide solution is being added. The colour turns a brilliant emerald-green when the point of inflexion is passed. The green colour sometimes develops only on keeping, often when an excess of ferrocyanide has been added.

The authors thank Principal M. Q. Doja for his kind interest in this work.

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Received December 11, 1956

